

The rolling marker.

The new rolling marker provides an easy system for marking planting distances.

connected by flat outer beams that make the straight lines at 25 or 20 cm.

The use of the roller provides an easy system for marking 20 × 20-cm, 20 × 25-cm, or 25 × 25-cm planting distances. These different distances are achieved by changing the outer beam from four to five pieces or by shifting the movable wheels and joining the two wheels in the center together to make a distance of 25 × 25 cm. The marker is efficient because it makes cross lines as planting markers in only one pass. The marker is also lighter and has less soil draft than the traditional marker.

The materials required to construct a rolling marker are (1) a 5-m-long wood beam (3 × 4 cm) for the axis and outer beam, (2) a 5-m-long wood beam (20 × 2 cm) for the six-piece wheels, (3) a 2-m-long L-shaped iron (0.5-inch) for the frame (wood can be used if necessary), and (4) two bearings for the wheels.

A modified area sampler for aquatic invertebrate assemblages in flooded rice

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Takahashi et al (1982) invented a two-enclosure "area sampler" for sampling floodwater invertebrates in California rice fields. In this note, we report on some design modifications and performance characteristics of the area sampler (hereafter called floodwater collector) for use in tropical irrigated rice fields.

Our version uses a pair of metal cylinders (instead of two square boxes used by Takahashi et al), one serving as an outer cylinder made from galvanized tin ("A" cylinder), and an inner cylinder ("B" cylinder) functioning as a plunger made from stainless steel (see figure). Cylinder A is bottomless with fifteen 3.3-cm holes drilled along its bottom edge to allow passage of aquatic invertebrates. It is fitted with a 7.5-cm-wide collar that functions as a hole cover and adjustable clamp during sam-

pling. Cylinder B has two handles and a central 5-cm hole in its bottom to accommodate a #11 rubber stopper. Multiple units of cylinder A can be made as needed to obtain the desired sample size; however, only one unit of cylinder B is required. The diameter of the collector can be adjusted to fit local planting practices. No matter what diameter is used, water volume must be recorded for each sample to obtain population density estimates.

The field operation of our collector requires 2 consecutive days: the first day to sink the A cylinders in the field, and the second day to take samples. On day 1, the A cylinders are centered over single rice plants (or hills) and collars are clamped above the 15 access holes. The passage of 1 d between placement and collection allows water and organisms to reequilibrate

in the field following initial disturbance. (Takahashi et al located and gathered their samples all on the same day.) On day 2, the collars are lowered and clamped tightly around the access holes to prevent escape of invertebrates. The rice plant is removed, rinsed to remove attached invertebrates, and set aside. Next, the operator grasps the B cylinder by the handles and plunges it into the A cylinder to expel water and trapped organisms through the 5-cm hole. After expelling all the remaining water, the operator inserts the rubber stopper into the B cylinder and pulls it out while standing on the metal supports of the A cylinder.

Inspecting the mud for additional invertebrates underneath the B cylinder will ensure a more representative catch. Depending on water depth and season,

Two-cylinder apparatus (A and B) and 2-d sampling design for collecting invertebrate communities from the floodwater zone of the rice ecosystem.

Catches of aquatic invertebrates using the floodwater collector and three other methods at three crop stages, IRRI Farm, 1997-98.

Method	Vegetative stage		Reproductive stage		Ripening stage	
	Taxa ^a (no.)	Organisms (no.)	Taxa ^a (no.)	Organisms (no.)	Taxa ^a (no.)	Organisms (no.)
Floodwater collector	30 (20.6 ± 3.7)	2,453	32 (24.9 ± 3.3)	2,208	28 (24.3 ± 2.7)	1,568
FARMCOP	21 (20.0 ± 1.7)	519	25 (23.3 ± 2.3)	741	27 (26.4 ± 1.4)	835
Rice-vac	24 (24)	438	28 (24.7 ± 2.9)	983	26 (24.7 ± 2.0)	979
Strainer-net	27 (18.1 ± 3.8)	1,470	28 (28)	593	27 (27)	715

^aObserved number of taxa and expected (rarefaction-adjusted) number of taxa (mean ± 2 standard deviations). Numbers are counts from 10 samples of 0.1 m² each, for a total planar area of 1 m².

which may vary between 3 and 10 cm deep in Philippine irrigated fields, the B cylinder collects 1-6 L of paddy water in a funnel. The water is then passed through an 86-mesh microscreen and transferred to vials containing 70% ethanol.

A comparison of invertebrate catches of the floodwater collector, FARMCOP (Cariño et al 1979), Rice-vac (Domingo and Schoenly 1998), and strainer-net methods (Schoenly et al 1998)

showed that the collector catches more organisms and more taxa than the other methods. After standardizing (rarefying) invertebrate abundances to a common size (Simberloff 1972), all methods gave statistically comparable counts of taxa during the vegetative stage. At later crop stages, the strainer-net caught (slightly) more taxa than the other methods (see table). Its higher catch is due in part to a deeper scooping motion that tended to dislodge more mud and its associated fauna.

The materials for the A and B cylinders of the floodwater collector cost approximately US\$15 and \$20, respectively. The addition of a vial caddy (Domingo and Schoenly 1998) to aid sampling allows two persons to comfortably operate the cylinders. The floodwater collector may undersample the benthic fauna, but it shows promise as an easy-to-use, inexpensive, and time-effective method for conducting studies on biodiversity assessment, ecological monitoring, and environmental

impacts of farmer interventions on rice-invertebrate assemblages at and below the water line.

References

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Socioeconomics

Medicinal weeds in rice fields of Chhattisgarh, India

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We conducted an ethnobotanical survey in Raipur during 1995-98 to identify medicinal weeds in rice fields in Chhattisgarh and document their uses. The survey, undertaken in upland, medium-elevation, and lowland areas, covered all kinds of weeds. Weeds were collected and their habitat and medicinal properties were noted after identification. To determine the uses of medicinal weeds, more than 60 farmers were interviewed. Folk doctors, *tantriks* (people who practice *tantra*), *baigas* (people who cure diseases with herbal medicines, assisted by spiritual power), and Ayurvedic doctors (doctors who practice *Ayurveda*, one of India's oldest systems of medicine) were consulted on the medicinal value of weeds.

The survey revealed that more than 50 weed species infest the rice fields of Chhattisgarh. Of these, more than 35 spe-

cies have been reported in ancient Indian literature as medicinal plants. The survey also showed that Chhattisgarh farmers use more than 25 species of medicinal weeds to solve their health problems. The medicinal uses of some problematic weeds are shown in the table. The study suggested a

strong need to document valuable knowledge about medicinal weeds from experienced farmers. By knowing the medicinal uses of weeds and identifying a suitable market for them, farmers can earn extra income from these unwanted plants.

Medicinal weeds in rice fields, Chhattisgarh, India.

Weed species	Local name	Medicinal uses
<i>Cyperus scariosus</i>	Motha	For fever
<i>Fimbristylis</i> sp.	Chuhaka	For stomach disorders
<i>Kyllingia monocephala</i>	Bandarphool	Anti-venom
<i>Abutilon indicum</i>	Raksi	Leaves used for bleeding piles Seeds used for treating cough
<i>Phyllanthus niruri</i>	Bhuinawla	For jaundice
<i>Eclipta alba</i>	Bhengra	For respiratory problems
<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	Duddhi	For respiratory problems
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	Doobi	For hysteria, epilepsy, and insanity
<i>Echinochloa colonum</i>	Sawan	For stomach disorders
<i>Oxalis corniculata</i>	Khattibuti	For skin eruptions

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